

Estimating Treatment Effects using Machine Learning

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1 Introduction

In the past, data on economic activity was relatively scarce. However, recent developments have changed the situation substantially in a short period of time: Contemporary datasets are available faster, have greater scope and coverage, and often possess a more complex structure. Furthermore, while it has been common practice in empirical economics and econometrics to look for research designs that might help identify the “average treatment effect” of particular policies (see Imbens and Wooldridge (2009) for an overview), nowadays large-scale data with rich individual characteristics allow for finer estimates of the effects of different policies. Consequently, considerable interest in developing flexible and performant methods for heterogeneous treatment effect estimation has been evoked.¹ Some notable recent proposals include adaptations of the lasso (Imai and Ratkovic (2013)), neural networks (Shalit et al. (2017)), BART (Hill (2011)), random forests (Athey et al. (2019)), recursive partitioning (Athey and Imbens (2016); Su et al. (2009)), as well as combinations thereof (Künzel et al. (2019)); Nie and Wager (2017)); see Dorie et al. (2019) for a recent survey.

Unfortunately, there is no conclusive guidance on how to tailor existing generic machine learning predictors into good treatment effect estimators that are robust to confounding. In this work, I therefore want to give an overview about some “meta-algorithms” that adopt a different perspective: Instead of developing “causal” variants of specific machine learning methods, these meta-learners can take advantage of any supervised learning or regression method (the so called base-learner) to estimate the Conditional Average Treatment Effect (CATE) function. Thereupon, the focus will be on the X-learner algorithm that was proposed by Künzel et al. (2019) and the core of the authors’ theoretical results. Afterwards, random forests as base learners in particular will be introduced and discussed with regard to one known weakness. The final simulation study then examines to what extent the X-learner equipped with a base learner that exploits the smoothness of the regression surface, can improve on state-of-the-art methods with regard to several data generating processes from the literature. The simulation results are promising, although the overall stability of the method has to be further analyzed in a wider theoretical context.

2 The Framework

2.1 The Neyman-Rubin causal model

Originating from the work of Neyman (1923), Cochran and Chambers (1965), Rubin (1974) and Holland (1986), the “Neyman-Rubin causal model” (sometimes also called the “Potential outcomes framework”) has become increasingly popular across

¹The issue of heterogeneous treatment effect estimation in observational studies does not only arise in economics, but in a wide variety of applications, see e.g., Obermeyer and Emanuel (2016) and Wendling et al. (2018) for examples from personalized medicine.

scientific fields. Neyman (1923) introduced the framework as a non-parametric model where each unit is characterised by two potential outcomes: one if it is untreated and the other if treated (or *exposed to the cause*). Even though Rubin (1974) and Cochran and Chambers (1965) developed the model into a more general framework for causal inference, I will focus on the binary treatment case in this article. Furthermore, I will here follow the notation of Künzel et al. (2019). So if we have a distribution \mathcal{P} from which a realization of N independent random variables is drawn, i.e. $(Y_i(0), Y_i(1), X_i, W_i) \sim \mathcal{P}$, where $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the d -dimensional covariate vector² and $W_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the treatment assignment indicator, then $Y_i(0) \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the potential outcome of unit i that could be observed if i were assigned to the control group, whereas $Y_i(1) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the potential outcome of i under treatment. This means that only one of the two potential outcomes is observable:

$$Y_i = W_i Y_i(1) + (1 - W_i) Y_i(0) \quad (1)$$

This fact is also called the *fundamental problem of causal inference* and implies that the *individual treatment effect (ITE)*, defined as $D_i := Y_i(1) - Y_i(0)$ of W_i on Y_i is never observed. However, the identification of the average treatment effect (ATE), defined as $ATE := \mathbb{E}[Y(1) - Y(0)]$, is possible under mild assumptions and standard in microeconometrics (see, e.g., Imbens and Wooldridge (2009)). The focus of this study is on conditional average treatment effects (CATEs). There are several possible conditioning levels:

$$IATE \equiv \tau(x) := \mathbb{E}[D \mid X = x] = \mathbb{E}[Y(1) - Y(0) \mid X = x] \quad (2)$$

$$GATE \equiv \tau(g) := \mathbb{E}[D \mid G = g] = \int \tau(x) f_{X \mid G=g}(x) dx$$

$$ATE \equiv \tau := \mathbb{E}[D] = \mathbb{E}[Y(1) - Y(0)]$$

The *individualized average treatment effect (IATE)* conditions on all available covariates X_i , whereas the *group average treatment effect (GATE)* conditions on pre-defined groups, G_i , of covariates and corresponds to a coarser aggregation level. Throughout this paper I will focus on the finest aggregation level, the IATE. As the later discussed X-learner approach uses the notation $CATE \equiv IATE$, I will follow this convention from here on. Our final aim is to use statistical methods to estimate the CATE function, as this estimator is at the same time MSE-optimal with regard to the ITE (Lemma 2). However, in order to identify the CATE estimates from observable data and avoid bias in non-randomized trials, we need the following assumptions:

A1 (Unconfoundedness / Strong ignorability):

$$Y_i(1), Y_i(0) \perp W_i \mid X_i = x, \forall x \in \mathcal{R}_{X_i} \text{ (the support of } X_i)$$

²In this specification X_i represents the union of confounding variables and heterogeneity features for notational convenience. In principle, these might be completely, partly or non-overlapping (see e.g., Knaus et al. (2017))

A2 (Common support / Overlap):

$$0 < e_{min} < P[W_i = 1 | X_i = x] = e(x) < e_{max} < 1, \forall x \in \mathcal{R}_{X_i}$$

A3 (Exogeneity of covariates): $X_i(1) = X_i(0), \forall i = 1, \dots, N$

A4 (Stable Unit Treatment Value): $Y_{(W_1, W_2, \dots, W_N), i} = Y_{(W'_1, W'_2, \dots, W'_N), i}$ if $\forall j : W_j = W'_j$, where $Y_i = Y_{W_i, i} = W_i Y_i(1) + (1 - W_i) Y_i(0)$.

The unconfoundedness assumption rules out hidden confounders, stating that the treatment assignment is as good as random once we control for the covariates X_i (Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983)).³ The common support assumes the conditional treatment probability (hereafter: propensity score $e(x)$) to be bounded away from zero and one. Furthermore, exogeneity specifies that the covariates are not affected by the treatment. Finally, the last assumption (SUTVA) can be split into two sub-requirements: Firstly, it requires that there is no inference between units, i.e. potential outcomes for a unit must not be affected by treatment for any other units (no spill-over effects), and secondly, that there do not exist different versions of treatment (also called stability and consistency). As this is a more complicated assumption, see Brady (2002) for a discussion. Note also that even though not mentioned in their work, Künzel et al. (2019) (KSBY hereafter) rely on this essential assumption.

Let us now define the following representation of \mathcal{P} , where $\mu_1(x) := \mathbb{E}[Y(1) | X = x]$ and $\mu_0(x) := \mathbb{E}[Y(0) | X = x]$:

$$\begin{aligned} X &\sim \Lambda, & Y(0) &= \mu_0(X) + \epsilon(0) \\ W &\sim \text{Bern}(e(X)), & Y(1) &= \mu_1(X) + \epsilon(1), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where Λ is the marginal distribution of X , $\epsilon(0)$ and $\epsilon(1)$ are zero-mean random variables and independent of X and W . Note that within this specification, **A1** implies that $(\epsilon(1), \epsilon(0)) \perp W | X$. At this point, let me introduce a second way of writing this model that will be helpful later. Using (3), we can rewrite (1) as:

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= WY(1) + (1 - W)Y(0) \\ &= \mu_0(X) + W \cdot \tau(X) + \gamma(W), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma(W) = W \cdot \epsilon(1) + (1 - W) \cdot \epsilon(0)$, such that $\mathbb{E}[\gamma(W) | X] = 0$. Now, while the ITE is not identifiable without strong additional assumptions⁴, the CATE can be estimated from data:

Lemma 1. *Under **A1-A4** and regularity conditions ensuring the existence of appropriate moments, $\tau(x) := \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0) | X_i = x]$ (2) is identified from observable data.*

³This is an equivalent way of saying that there are no unobserved covariates that influence both the treatment variable, W , and one or both of the potential outcomes $Y(0), Y(1)$.

⁴See Künzel et al. (2019) Appendix B for an example.

Hence, we can use estimates of $\tau(x)$ to gain insights about the true individual treatment effects D_i (ITE). The following short, but important Lemma illustrates the relation between ITEs and CATEs:

Lemma 2. *Let $O_n = (Y_i, X_i, W_i)_{i=1}^n$ be the set of observed data. Let $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$ be a measurable function of x and the data, O_n , that estimates the true treatment effect function $D(x)$. Then, the L_2 risk: $\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - D(X))^2 \mid O_n]$ of $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$ satisfies,*

$$\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - D(X))^2 \mid O_n] = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} (\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x) + \mathbb{E}[(\tau(X) - D(X))^2] \quad (5)$$

where the integral is called the L_2 error of $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$, μ denotes the distribution of X and the integration is with respect to the Lebesgue measure. Then, the L_2 risk of the estimate $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$ is close to the optimal value iff the L_2 error is close to zero.

As I will later present some theoretic results of the X-learner with respect to the Expected Mean Squared Error (EMSE) of the CATE function, this result will be particularly useful.

3 Estimation approaches

From Lemma 1 we can (under **A1-A4**) write and identify the CATE function as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x) &= \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0) \mid X_i = x] = \mu_1(x) - \mu_0(x) \quad (6) \\ &= \mathbb{E}[Y_i \mid W_i = 1, X_i = x] - \mathbb{E}[Y_i \mid W_i = 0, X_i = x] \\ &= \mu_1^*(x) - \mu_0^*(x) \end{aligned}$$

This shows that the fundamental task is to estimate the difference of two conditional expectations; however, due to the *fundamental problem of Causal Inference*, we never observe these differences at an individual level and have to estimate them in two disjoint subpopulations. This fact makes the estimation of CATE a non-standard machine learning problem. Consequently, there is a variety of approaches to tackle this challenge: On the one hand several generic approaches (also referred to as meta-algorithms) that split the causal estimation problem into several standard prediction problems and then use any suitable base learner to solve those have been suggested. These meta-algorithms allow a flexible choice of different base-learners that fit a particular type of data, while at the same time taking advantage of more general asymptotic results for the given meta-learner.⁵

On the other hand, a thriving literature around problem specific machine learning estimators such as the Causal Forests (Athey et al. (2019)) or BART (Hill (2011)) has evolved. In what follows, I will first present some of the common generic approaches and then address the X-learner (KSBY) in more detail.

⁵Obviously, this flexibility is only a gain, if the base learners match the features of the data as well as the underlying model well.

3.1 The T-learner

A straightforward meta-learner approach follows directly from equation (6). This approach is sometimes called the *T-learner* and takes the difference of the conditional expectations estimated in the two disjoint samples of treated and non-treated separately.⁶ Any base-learner (potentially different ones for treated and non-treated units) can be used to estimate the conditional outcome means $\hat{\mu}_w(x)$:

$$\hat{\tau}_{TL}(x) = \hat{\mu}_1(x) - \hat{\mu}_0(x) \quad (7)$$

However, it may be problematic to use this approach when estimating a CATE function with different sizes of treatment and control groups. To see why, let us *w.l.o.g.* assume for a moment that the treated group is much smaller in size than the control group. By construction, the T-learner cannot use information from the control group to achieve better estimators for the treatment group. This can result in an aggregation of conditional regression functions of different complexities, which induces a much more complex CATE function than the regularization of the treatment group should allow.⁷ However, this problem does not only arise in unbalanced sample cases. Even in a balanced setting, the estimated treatment effect $\hat{\mu}_1(x) - \hat{\mu}_0(x)$ may be regularized away from the true CATE, due to the separate regularization process.⁸

3.2 The S-learner

The *S-learner* is another naïve meta-learning approach, which basically treats the indicator variable W as a covariate similar to all others. Therefore, the combined response surface to estimate is:

$$\mu(x, w) := \mathbb{E}[Y^{obs} \mid X = x, W = w]$$

Again, any base learner can be used, but this time on the entire data set. The CATE estimator is thus given by:

$$\hat{\tau}_{SL}(x) = \hat{\mu}(x, 1) - \hat{\mu}(x, 0) \quad (8)$$

In many cases, especially when random forests are used as base learners, this estimator seems to be biased towards zero, as the importance of the covariate W on the estimate is not significant enough (see Künzel et al. (2019) for simulation results).

⁶This approach is also referred to as Q-learning in Qian and Murphy (2011).

⁷See Künzel et al. (2019) for some extreme cases.

⁸See Nie and Wager (2017) for an example involving lasso.

3.3 Modified covariate and outcome methods

A convenient way to put the following approaches on common ground is to consider them as solutions of a weighted minimization problem with modified outcomes:

$$\min_{\tau} \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i [Y_i^* - \tau(X_i)]^2 \right\} \quad (9)$$

where Y_i^* represents potential outcome modifications, and adaptations of the weights w_i might originate from modified covariates.

3.3.1 The R-learner

The R-learner was proposed in Nie and Wager (2017) and is a representative from the modified covariate method.⁹ The criterion uses the transformation of Robinson (1988) on the Rubin model to motivate a loss function that can be minimized by any suitable base learner. It therefore uses the weights $w_i = (W_i - e(X_i))^2$ and the modified outcomes $Y_i^* = \frac{Y_i - m(X_i)}{W_i - e(X_i)}$, where $m(X_i) := \mathbb{E}[Y | X = x]$.¹⁰ The authors break the estimation process into two steps:

1. Fit $\hat{m}(x)$ and $\hat{e}(x)$ via methods tuned for optimal predictive accuracy. These functions are called “nuisance parameters”.
2. Estimate the treatment effect function $\hat{\tau}_{RL}(x)$ via a plug-in version of (9) with the weights and modified outcomes from above and the estimated nuisance parameters from step 1. Additionally, add a regularizer $\Lambda_N(\tau(\cdot))$ to (9) in order to control the complexity of the $\tau(\cdot)$ function.

Current implementations use a linear working model for the non-parametric function, i.e. $\tau(x) = x\beta$. This facilitates rewriting the weighted minimization problem as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{RL} = \arg \min_{\beta} \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left((W_i - \hat{e}(X_i)) \left[\frac{Y_i - \hat{m}(X_i)}{W_i - \hat{e}(X_i)} - X_i^{RL} \beta \right] \right)^2 + \Lambda_N(x\beta) \right\} \quad (10)$$

The estimated CATEs at point x can then be obtained by any suitable method that solves (10), by setting $\hat{\tau}_{RL}(x) = x\hat{\beta}_{RL}$. The authors prove that the R-learner has several strong convergence guarantees. In the case of penalized kernel regression they show the feasible estimator’s $\hat{\tau}_{RL}(x)$ convergence rates to depend only on the complexity of the true $\tau(\cdot)$, provided that the nuisance parameters $m(\cdot)$ and $e(\cdot)$ are estimated at $o(n^{-1/4})$ root-mean squared error rates. The error bounds of the feasible

⁹See Tian et al. (2014) for another modified covariate estimator (MCM). However, the MCM with efficiency augmentation performs very similar to the R-learning criterion, so I chose the R-learner as a benchmark for this class of estimators.

¹⁰For a derivation of this specification, see Appendix A.

estimator $\hat{\tau}_{RL}(x)$ asymptotically thus match the best available bounds for an oracle method that knows the true nuisance parameters while solving (10).¹¹

3.3.2 The X-learner

The X-learner algorithm was proposed by Künzel et al. (2019) and serves as the baseline of this paper. I will first introduce the several stages and idea behind the method, then provide some intuition and show that it can be seen as a representative of the class of modified outcome methods by writing it according to (9). Afterwards, some theoretical characteristics of the estimator will be presented and finally, in the simulation study, we will see how well the X-learner generalizes to situations of various complexity. Additionally, we will see whether one can improve the method by using local linear random forests as base learners in order to avoid poor performance at the boundaries.

Let me first specify the method:

1. Estimate the response surfaces $\mu_w(x) = \mathbb{E}[Y(w) \mid X = x]$ in the two disjoint samples with appropriate base learners. This step is equivalent to the T-learner. Denote the estimated functions as $\hat{\mu}_w(x)$, $w \in \{0, 1\}$.
2. Define pseudo-effects \tilde{D}_i^1 on the treated and \tilde{D}_i^0 on the control units as:

$$\tilde{D}_i^1 := Y_i^1 - \hat{\mu}_0(X_i^1), \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{D}_i^0 := \hat{\mu}_1(X_i^0) - Y_i^0, \quad (12)$$

where Y_i^1 and Y_i^0 (X_i^1 and X_i^0) represent the i th observed outcome (covariate vector) within the treated and control group, respectively. Note that the X-learner uses the control estimator $\hat{\mu}_0(\cdot)$ on the treatment data X_i^1 and vice versa. This is the correct way to impute the treatment effect estimate. Note also, that if $\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_0(x) \mid X = x] = \mu_0(x)$ and $\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_1(x) \mid X = x] = \mu_1(x)$, then $\tau(x) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{D}^1 \mid X = x] = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{D}^0 \mid X = x]$. Therefore, we can later interpret the X-learner as a modified outcome approach in accordance with (9).

3. As the imputed treatment effects are both approximations of the true treatment effect, we can use them to fit $\hat{\tau}_1(x)$ in the treatment group, and $\hat{\tau}_0(x)$ in the control group.
4. Aggregate the two treatment effect estimators as a linear combination:

$$\hat{\tau}_{XL}(x) = g(x)\hat{\tau}_0(x) + (1 - g(x))\hat{\tau}_1(x), \quad (13)$$

¹¹See Nie and Wager (2017) for more details on the R-learner.

where $g \in [0, 1]$ is a weight function.¹²

Now, we would like to understand the X-learner from a different, more common perspective that can be compared to alternative methods in the literature: By inspection of steps 2 and 3, we can see easily, that the X-learner solves (9) for both $\tau_1(x)$ and $\tau_0(x)$:

$$\hat{\tau}_1(x) = \arg \min_{\tau_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{w_i=1} \left(Y_i^1 - \hat{\mu}_0(X_i^1) - \tau_1(X_i^1) \right)^2 + \Lambda_{n_1}(\tau_1) \right\} \quad (14)$$

$$\hat{\tau}_0(x) = \arg \min_{\tau_0} \left\{ \frac{1}{n_0} \sum_{w_i=0} \left(\hat{\mu}_1(X_i^0) - Y_i^0 - \tau_0(X_i^0) \right)^2 + \Lambda_{n_0}(\tau_0) \right\}, \quad (15)$$

where n_0 and n_1 indicate the number of observations in the control and treatment group, respectively. Thus, the X-learner is basically a linear combination (or weighted average) of the $\hat{\tau}_w$ estimates generated by (9) in disjoint samples, with weights $w_i = 1$, as well as modified outcomes $Y_i^*(1) = \tilde{D}_i^1$ and $Y_i^*(0) = \tilde{D}_i^0$, respectively. Again, the regularizer Λ_{n_w} could be explicit as in penalized regressions, or implicit, e.g. as provided by a carefully designed neural network or random forest.¹³

Before we begin a more formal analysis of the X-learner, let us try to understand the idea behind the concept. A convenient way to do so, is to compare the X-learner steps to the baseline of the T-learner. For this purpose, recall that the T-learner method estimates the conditional outcome means $\mu_1(x)$ and $\mu_0(x)$ separately, such that in general, we cannot expect the $\hat{\tau}_{TL}(x)$ to approximate the CATE at a rate faster than the sum of the rates at which the two conditional outcome means are estimated (Theorem 1). However, in real data settings it often occurs that the treatment effect function has a simpler form than the two conditional potential outcome functions. Therefore, instead of splitting the problem of estimating the CATE into the two subproblems of estimating $\mu_1(x)$ and $\mu_0(x)$, we would like to make use of the form of the CATE. The X-learner does exactly that: Each of its treatment effect estimators $\hat{\tau}_0(x)$ and $\hat{\tau}_1(x)$ of step 3 consists of an estimator for the conditional outcome, $\hat{\mu}_w(X_i^{1-w})$, and an estimator for the imputed treatment effects which should achieve a similar rate to the one of the CATE.¹⁴ This decomposition becomes even clearer when looking at (14,15), where the “nuisance parameter” is the estimator of the conditional outcome and the estimator for the imputed treatment effect results from the minimization problem itself. Therefore, if the CATE function has a simpler form

¹²While g can in principle be any weight function with the aim to achieve an improved $\hat{\tau}(x)$, Künzel et al. (2019) describe that, in practise, the propensity score function $e(x)$ is a good choice. However, in that case this nuisance parameter has to be estimated in an additional step and can then be used as a plug-in estimator, i.e. $g = \hat{e}$.

¹³In case of random forests a regularization can be achieved by the maximum depth of the single trees, the minimum number of samples a node must have, before it can split, or the minimum number of samples a leaf node must have, among others.

¹⁴Recall that $\tau(x) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{D}^w | X = x]$

and is thus easier to estimate than each of the two conditional potential outcome functions, the X-learner (with appropriate base learners and appropriate choice of $g(x)$) should achieve a better rate than the T-learner (Conjecture 1).

Additionally, the X-learner can use information from the control group to derive better estimates for the treatment group and vice versa. This alleviates the problem described in the T-learner section. The pooling of information should be evident from step 2 and 3 in the X-learner routine. An appropriate weighting in step 4 then ensures that the estimator $\hat{\tau}_w(x)$ which bases on more observations for a given neighbourhood of the covariate vector X , receives more weight.¹⁵

3.3.3 Theory

In order to formulate the above intuitions from a theoretical perspective and measure the quality of an estimate, we need some risk function for our estimate $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$. I follow Künzel et al. (2019) in using the L_2 risk: $\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - D(X))^2 | O_n]$. Due to Lemma 2, the minimization of the L_2 risk is equivalent to minimizing the L_2 error $\int_{\mathbb{R}^d} (\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x)$. However, the estimate $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$ depends on the data O_n , therefore the L_2 error is a random variable. I am interested in the convergence of the expectation of this random variable, thus taking expectations over $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$, which yields a representation of the $EMSE(\mathcal{P}, \hat{\tau}_n)$ that is equivalent to the one used by Künzel et al. (2019):

$$\begin{aligned} EMSE(\mathcal{P}, \hat{\tau}_n) &= \mathbb{E}_{\hat{\tau}} \left[\mathbb{E}_X \left[(\tau(X) - \hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n))^2 \right] \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\int (\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Note that for a fixed distribution \mathcal{P} there are always feasible estimators with small EMSE. However, in general, \mathcal{P} is unknown and there do not exist estimates for which the EMSE converges to zero at some fixed, nontrivial rate for all distributions.¹⁶ This is why we have to restrict the class of distributions, e.g., by imposing some smoothness assumptions on the regression functions. Now, the minimax approach analyzes the worst performance of an estimator over a given class or family, F , of distributions and defines an optimal rate of convergence for such classes:

$$R_n = \inf_{\hat{\tau}_n} \sup_{\mathcal{P} \in F} \mathbb{E} \int (\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x), \quad (17)$$

where the infimum is taken over all estimates $\hat{\tau}_n$ and, for simplicity, we are only interested in the asymptotic behavior of (17). Then R_n is called the minimax risk (or rate). In particular, the optimal estimate τ^* for the family of distributions in

¹⁵See Künzel et al. (2019) for an extensive example that demonstrates the effect of sharing of information among treatment groups.

¹⁶See e.g. Chapter 3 in Györfi et al. (2006).

(17) should yield a value close to the minimax risk. This brings us to the following definition from Künzel et al. (2019):

Definition 1. For $a \in (0, 1]$, define $S(a)$ to be the set of all families, F , with a minimax rate of at most N^{-a} .

By definition, for a given family $F \in S(a)$, there exists an optimal estimator τ^* that reaches this rate N^{-a} (except for a constant) for all $N \geq 1$:

$$\sup_{\mathcal{P} \in F} \mathbb{E} \int (\tau_n^*(x, O_n) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x) \leq CN^{-a}. \quad (18)$$

As specified before, we assume a super-population of random variables according to some distribution $(Y(0), Y(1), X, W) \sim \mathcal{P}$. Let me now follow Künzel et al. (2019) and introduce superpopulations with given rates:

Definition 2. Recall the general characterization of \mathcal{P} in (3). For $a_\mu, a_\tau \in (0, 1]$, define $S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$ to be the set of all families of distributions \mathcal{P} , such that

B1 assumptions **A1-A4** hold,

B2 the distribution of $(X, Y(0))$ given $W = 0$ is in a class $F_{\mu_0} \in S(a_\mu)$,

B3 the distribution of $(X, Y(1))$ given $W = 1$ is in a class $F_{\mu_1} \in S(a_\mu)$,

B4 the distribution of $(X, \mu_1(X) - Y(0))$ given $W = 0$ is in a class $F_{\tau_0} \in S(a_\tau)$,

B5 the distribution of $(X, Y(1) - \mu_0(X))$ given $W = 1$ is in a class $F_{\tau_1} \in S(a_\tau)$.

Given this framework, KSBY confirm our intuition from the preceding section regarding the T-learner:

Theorem 1. For $\mathcal{P} \in S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$, there exist base learners to be used on the T-learner, so that the corresponding T-learner estimates the CATE at a rate of

$$\mathcal{O}(m^{-a_\mu} + n^{-a_\tau}),^{17} \quad (19)$$

where m is the number of observations in the control group and n in the treatment group. In general, one cannot expect the rate to be any faster.

Therefore, as discussed before heuristically, the base learners' minimax optimal rates a_μ from the conditional mean regressions directly translate to rates for estimating $\hat{\tau}_{TL}(x)$. On the other hand, the X-learner's structure, with its two estimators $\hat{\tau}_0$ and $\hat{\tau}_1$, each consisting of an estimator for the respective outcome with rate a_μ and an estimator for the imputed treatment effect which should achieve a rate of at most a_τ , lead KSBY to the following conjecture:

¹⁷See KSBY Appendix H for a proof.

Conjecture 1. *Under some conditions on $\mathcal{P} \in S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$, there exist base learners such that $\hat{\tau}_0$ and $\hat{\tau}_1$ in the X-learner achieve the minimax rates,*

$$\mathcal{O}(m^{-a_\tau} + n^{-a_\mu}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{O}(m^{-a_\mu} + n^{-a_\tau}), \quad (20)$$

respectively.

Note that if this conjecture holds and we assume *w.l.o.g.* that the control units are outnumbering the treated units $m \gg n$ by far, then:

1. The bound on the EMSE (expected L_2 error) of the T-learner is dominated by the conditional mean estimation problem for the treated group,

$$\sup_{\mathcal{P} \in F} \mathbb{E} \int (\hat{\tau}_{n,m}^{TL}(x, O_{n,m}) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x) \leq Cn^{-a_\mu}. \quad (21)$$

2. The bound on the EMSE (expected L_2 error) of the X-learner, when setting $g = 0$, is dominated by the estimation problem for the imputed treatment effect,

$$\sup_{\mathcal{P} \in F} \mathbb{E} \int (\hat{\tau}_{n,m}^{XL}(x, O_{n,m}) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x) \leq C_2 n^{-a_\tau}, \quad (22)$$

where we used assumptions **B3** and **B5** from Definition 2. This is of course particularly useful in situations in which the treatment effect has a simpler form than the conditional means, i.e. for classes $F \in S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$ such that $a_\tau > a_\mu$. Additionally, in these situations and under Conjecture 1, setting the weight function g appropriately will also give better performance of the X-learner over the T-learner in a balanced treatment-control design. Unfortunately, even though the authors suspect the conjecture to hold in great generality, they can only prove the statement in two particular cases:

1. The conjecture holds under some technical conditions on \mathcal{P} for all families of distributions $F \in S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$ where the CATE is linear, i.e. $a_\tau = 1$ and no regularity conditions are imposed on the response functions. In this case the X-learner rate is minimax optimal (Theorem 2, *Appendix A*).
2. The conjecture holds under some technical conditions on \mathcal{P} for all families of distributions $F \in S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$ where the CATE is of the same order as the response functions, i.e. $a_\mu \approx a_\tau$ and the response functions are Lipschitz continuous. In this case the rate is also minimax optimal (Theorem 7, *KSBY Appendix I.3*).

4 Random forests

Random forests have received tremendous attention in recent years, as the method follows, in its basic form, a simple construction rule, but can be seen as one of the

most powerful machine learning algorithms available today. Consequently, random forests can frequently be encountered as base learners for meta algorithms such as the X-learner. In the simulation study of this paper, I address a particular weakness of random forests and analyze in how far different meta-learners can help enhancing their performance. Thus, it will be helpful to give a short introduction to the general method before applying it to various data generating processes (DGPs).

4.1 Regression trees

As trees are the fundamental components of random forests, I will shortly provide an overview, with a focus on regression trees. Regression trees are versatile machine learning algorithms capable of fitting complex datasets. Given n observations of pairs $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$, where X_i is a d -dimensional vector of covariates and Y_i the response, a regression tree partitions the covariate space into a set of “rectangles” and then usually fits a constant in each one. Focusing here only on the common CART algorithm (Classification and regression tree by Breiman (2001)), this method “grows a tree” by recursively finding the best binary splits, given the MSE loss function, i.e. solving the following minimization problem in each step:

$$\min_{j,s} \left\{ \sum_{i:x_i \in C_1(j,s)} (y_i - \bar{y}_1)^2 + \sum_{i:x_i \in C_2(j,s)} (y_i - \bar{y}_2)^2 \right\}, \quad (23)$$

where j is a potential splitting variable, s a split point and $C_1(j, s)$, $C_2(j, s)$ the induced pair of half-planes (child nodes),

$$C_1(j, s) := \{X \mid X_j < s\} \quad \text{and} \quad C_2(j, s) := \{X \mid X_j > s\}. \quad (24)$$

The algorithm thus first splits the whole training set in two subsets using a single covariate j and a threshold s that minimizes the cost function (23). Once it has successfully split the training set, it continues using the same logic on the subsets and so on, recursively.¹⁸ Suppose that the final tree is partitioned into M leafs (end nodes) L_1, L_2, \dots, L_M . Then to obtain an estimate for a fixed test point x_0 , the response is modeled as:

$$T(x_0) = \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{y}_m \cdot \mathbb{1}(x_0 \in L_m), \quad (25)$$

which is simply the average response of all training data points assigned to the leaf L_m^* that x_0 falls into. Obviously, since regression trees make very few structural assumptions about the training data, they are prone to overfitting when left unregularized, as can be seen in the left panel of Figure 1. To mitigate this issue, one

¹⁸Note that the CART algorithm is a greedy algorithm: it searches for an optimum split at the top level, then repeats the process at each level. It does not consider whether or not the split will lead to the lowest possible MSE several levels down. As finding the optimal tree is known to be an *NP-complete* problem, requiring $\mathcal{O}(\exp(n))$ time, and thus computationally infeasible, we must settle for a reasonably good solution, provided by CART.

Figure 1: Left panel: Fully grown regression tree to quadratic data without regularization. Right panel: Regression tree with a regularization on its maximal depth.

can restrict the trees' freedom by setting a maximum depth of the tree or making a requirement on the minimum number of samples a leaf node must have. Some practical experience from the literature recommends to first grow a large tree until some minimum node size¹⁹ is reached and then *prune* this large tree by cost complexity pruning.²⁰ However, one of the main issues with (regression) trees that cannot be resolved easily by regularization is their high variance: they are very sensitive to small variations in the training data by tending to select completely different series of splits and thus make interpretation difficult. This instability can be limited by averaging predictions over many trees, which leads us to *bagging* and *random forests*.

4.2 Bagging and random forests

Bootstrap aggregation (or bagging) is a general technique to reduce the variance of an estimated prediction function. Let us assume that we observe training data $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$ as before. In essence and the case of regression trees, bagging takes a collection of bootstrap samples Z_b^* , $b = 1, 2, \dots, B$ of size n from the training data and then grows a regression tree T_b on each bootstrapped data separately. Finally, to make a prediction at point x , the bagging estimate averages the predictions of each single tree,

$$\hat{f}^B(x) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B T_b(x) \quad (26)$$

If regression trees are grown sufficiently deep, it should be intuitively evident from the example in Figure 1 that they have a relatively low bias, but high variance (frequently referred to as instability). Therefore, the averaging can greatly benefit trees in reducing its prime factor of error.

To see the mechanism, note that since each tree grown via bagging is identically distributed (sampled from the same distribution), the expectation of the average of B such trees equals the expectation of any of them. Consequently, the bias of

¹⁹This minimum node size should be adaptively chosen from the data, e.g. by cross-validation.

²⁰See chapter 9 in Friedman et al. (2001) for more details.

the bagging predictor is the same as that of each individual tree and one can show the following decomposition of the pointwise expected generalization error of the ensemble, $\hat{f}_{\mathcal{T}}^B$, of B identically distributed trees, $T_b(x)$, given a training set \mathcal{T} at point x ,

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{T}}[L(y, \hat{f}_{\mathcal{T}}^B(x))] = \text{var}(x) + \text{bias}^2(x) + \text{noise}(x), \quad (27)$$

where L is the squared error loss function and,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{noise}(x) &= L(y, f(x)) & \text{bias}^2(x) &= \left(f(x) - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{T}}[T_b(x)]\right)^2, \\ \text{var}(x) &= \rho(x)\sigma_{\mathcal{T}}^2(x) + \frac{1 - \rho(x)}{B}\sigma_{\mathcal{T}}^2(x), \end{aligned}$$

where $\rho(x)$ is the sampling correlation between any pair of trees used in averaging, and $\sigma_{\mathcal{T}}^2(x)$ is the sampling variance of any randomly drawn tree. Here, the noise term only depends on the intrinsic randomness of Y and therefore stays the same, no matter the learning algorithm. As heuristically discussed above, the bias of the ensemble of trees is the same as the bias of any of those. On the other hand, as B gets arbitrarily large, the variance of the bagging (ensemble) function at point x reduces to $\text{var}(x) = \rho(x)\sigma_{\mathcal{T}}^2(x)$. As bootstrap sampling generates individual trees that are not perfectly correlated (see instability argument in 5.1), $\rho < 1$, and thus we establish three observations from this decomposition:

1. Since the variance of an ensemble is strictly smaller than the variance of an individual tree, its expected generalization error is also smaller. Therefore, improvements in prediction are solely the result of variance reduction.
2. As $B \rightarrow \infty$, the generalization error is bounded.²¹
3. The variance reduction of bagging can be improved by reducing ρ .

However, decorrelating trees further via ρ needs to be done carefully, so as to increase bias and individual tree variance as little as possible. *Random forests* are a popular concept for achieving this: While the method usually relies on bootstrapping as does bagging, further decorrelation of the individual trees is achieved by selecting $m : m < d$ of the covariates randomly as splitting candidates *at each split*. m can thus be seen as the crucial tuning parameter, trading a higher bias for a lower (ensemble) variance as it decreases. The final estimator thus has a form close to (26),

$$\hat{f}_{rf}^B(x) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B T(x, \Theta_b), \quad (28)$$

²¹For a formal proof, see Theorem 1.2 in Breiman (2001). Breiman concludes random forests cannot "overfit", but while it is a nice property that the generalization error is bounded, it is not necessarily small. Obviously, fully grown, unregularized individual trees that compose the ensemble can yield a high $\sigma_{\mathcal{T}}^2$. Segal (2004) shows small gains in performance by controlling the depths of individual trees, however, most authors suggest that using full-grown trees seldom costs much, see e.g., Friedman et al. (2001).

where Θ_b characterizes the b th tree of the random forest in terms of split variables, m , cutpoints at each node, and terminal-node (leaf) values.

5 Simulation study

5.1 The boundary issue

One weakness of nearest neighbor approaches in general, and random forests in particular, is that they trim down the hills and fill in the valleys of the true function to estimate. As can be seen in the left panel of Figure 2, the prediction surface of standard random forests resembles a step function as opposed to a smooth curve. This leads to a bias that is most dramatic in regions of high curvature, especially near the edge of feature space. One approach to tackle this issue is to view random forests from another angle: Instead of thinking about an ensemble method, random forests can also be interpreted as an adaptive kernel method.²² This becomes clear when rewriting the generated prediction function (28) in a different manner:

$$\hat{f}_{rf}^B(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i(x) Y_i, \quad (29)$$

where $\alpha_i(x)$ denotes the weight to the i -th unit generated by the forest when predicting at x .²³ From this perspective, forests are not directly delivering predictions via summation of trees, but instead generate weights which can then in a second step be used for other predictors. In a more general form, Athey et al. (2019) make use of this concept by solving weighted estimating equations using weights from random forests. For our aim, it is natural to follow Friedberg et al. (2018) and use the weights from (29) to solve the locally weighted standard least squares problem for the conditional mean function:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \hat{f}(x) \\ \hat{\theta}(x) \end{pmatrix} = \arg \min_{f, \theta} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i(x) (Y_i - f(x) - (x_i - x)\theta(x))^2 + \lambda_n \|\theta(x)\|_2^2 \right\}, \quad (30)$$

where $\hat{f}(x)$ estimates the conditional mean function $f(x)$, $\theta(x)$ corrects for local trends and $\lambda_n \|\theta(x)\|_2^2$ prevents overfitting to the local trend.²⁴ This representation has the advantage, that we can build on the large literature on local linear regression and how it can help to correct for potential misalignment by fitting straight lines rather than constants locally. Obviously, we can only remove bias to first order, but as the CATE function is in many use cases of limited complexity²⁵, an improvement

²²This view is advocated by Hothorn et al. (2004), Meinshausen (2006) and Athey et al. (2019).

²³See Appendix A for a short derivation of this form.

²⁴This is the standard form for local linear regression except of the ridge penalty term. This is needed for theoretic convergence results and attributes to the fact that we do not have a smoothing parameter h as in standard kernel regression that can be optimized. Instead the kernel is implicitly generated by the random forest, see Friedberg et al. (2018) for details.

²⁵See Kalla and Broockman (2018) or Sekhon and Shem-Tov (2017).

Figure 2: Estimating the CATE function $\tau(x) = \log(1 + \exp(X_1))$ (solid black line) at 500 test points, with $n = 1000$, $d = 20$, $X_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 2), \forall i$. Left panel: Standard random forests as base-learners for the X-learner (X-RF). Right panel: local linear corrected random forests on the X-learner (“X-LLF”) in red and “Local linear causal forests” (“LLCF”) in green (Friedberg et al. (2018)).

in prediction accuracy via local linear regression would carry over to a large variety of situations.

Note that as discussed earlier, the base learners of the X-learner can be chosen flexibly, so it would make sense to combine the X-learner meta-algorithm with the local linear regression from Friedberg et al. (2018). Since the X-learner is made to adapt to structural properties such as smoothness of the CATE function, it would be interesting to consider its performance when equipped with the local linear forests, as these also exploit smoothness in the regression surface. To be specific, carrying out step 3 of the X-learner via local linear regression should be the most beneficial application. In order to have a fair benchmark, I will compare this configuration of the X-learner to the “Local linear causal forests” in Friedberg et al. (2018). The method basically takes a forest kernel, α_i , and then uses a variant of the R-learner meta-algorithm from section 3.3 to estimate the treatment effect.²⁶

5.2 Simulation setup

In this simulation study the focus is on the performance of the X-learner and “Local linear causal forests” (LLCF), which can be seen as an application of the R-learner, with respect to several data generating processes (DGPs). For better assessment of performance, the T-learner from section 3.1 is also considered. In all simulations the relevant quantity to estimate is the CATE function. All simulations are implemented using methods from the “causalToolbox” R package by Sören Künzel or the “grf” R

²⁶The authors introduce a modification of the CART split for their random forests that is adjusted to local linear regression in a later step (see chapter 2.1) and yields different weights. When comparing the R-learner described in this paper and their variant, the difference lies in the usage of weighting according to forest weights α_i and the addition of a regularized adjustment for local linear regression (see equation (12) in Friedberg et al. (2018) and Appendix A for a comparison).

package by Julie Tibshirani, Susan Athey, and Stefan Wager. In case of the X-learner, local linear forests (X-LLF), standard random forests (X-RF) and BART (X-BART, Hill (2011)) are considered as base learners; for the T-learner, standard random forests (T-RF) are used as a general benchmark and in case of LLCF, the general random forests (GRF) from Athey et al. (2019) are added for the sake of completeness.²⁷ These GRF are closely related to the T-learner method (with random forests as base learners), as they can be written in a similar manner.²⁸ By construction of the methods, I expect the X-learner paired with local linear forests as its base-learner (X-LLF), as well as LLCF to achieve the best performance in situations as described in 6.1. However, I will also simulate situations where one expects the T-learner to perform better. In all simulations, I generate data as follows: for different choices of the marginal distribution $X \sim \Lambda_d$ indexed by dimension d , the noise level σ , the propensity function $e(x)$, a *baseline main effect* $b(x)$, and treatment effect function $\tau(x)$:

$$\begin{aligned} X_i &\sim \Lambda_d, & W_i &\sim \text{Bern}(e(X_i)), & \epsilon_i | X_i &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \\ Y_i &= b(X_i) + (W_i - 0.5)\tau(X_i) + \sigma\epsilon_i. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Motivated by Nie and Wager (2017), this is a more convenient way to initialize the setups compared to (3), without leading to inconsistencies. I consider four different setups:

Unbalanced design As follows from Theorem 2, the X-learner should perform well in unbalanced treatment designs. To test if the X-LLF can further enhance the standard X-RF in this setting, I reconsider Simulation 1 from KSBY with a minor change to the propensity score function.²⁹ As the CATE function is simpler than the d -dimensional baseline main effect, the X-learner should further improve on the T-learner. Thus the setting follows: $X_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, $e(X_i) = 0.1$, $b(X_i) = X_i' \beta + 5 \cdot \mathbb{1}(X_{i1} > 0.5) + 4 \cdot \mathbb{1}(X_{i2} > 0.1)$, $\tau(x) = 8 \cdot \mathbb{1}(X_{i2} > 0.1)$, where $\beta \sim U([-5, 5]^d)$.

Boundary setting This setting is motivated by Setup B in Nie and Wager (2017). Note, that the treatment function resembles closely the response surface (1) in Friedberg et al. (2018), which serves as their motivating example for boundary correction of random forests via local linear regression. Therefore, and because the curvature of $\tau(x)$ is approximately of first order, this DGP can be used to analyze the boundary issue discussed before. Set: $X_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, $e(X_i) = 0.5$, $b(X_i) = \max\{X_{i1} + X_{i2}, X_{i3}, 0\} + \max\{X_{i4}, X_{i5}, 0\}$ and $\tau(x) = X_{i1} + (1 + e^{X_{i2}})$.

²⁷For more details on the tuning an implementation of the various base learners see Appendix B.

²⁸See Künzel et al. (2019) Appendix A for more details.

²⁹This change from $e(x) = 0.01$ to $e(x) = 0.1$ is needed to allow k-fold cross-validation within the LLF and X-LLF training. Otherwise, there do not exist enough observations per fold for small sample sizes.

Complex treatment Relating to the case $a_\mu \approx a_\tau$ in Conjecture 2, I follow KSBY with their complex non-linear setup in Simulation 3. Note that in this setup nothing can be learned from the other assignment group, so that the T-learner should perform optimally. Therefore set: $X_i \sim U([0, 1]^d)$, $e(X_i) = 0.5$, $b(X_i) = 0$, $\tau(x) = \zeta(X_{i1})\zeta(X_{i2})$, where $\zeta(x) = 2/(1 + e^{-20(x-1/3)})$.

Confounding This setup is motivated by Setup C in Nie and Wager (2017). The treatment effect is fixed at $\tau(x) = 1$ as the focus is to test the method's resistance to bias due to an interaction between $e(x)$ and $b(x)$. Especially in observational studies, treatment assignment can be correlated with potential outcomes, such that a good method has to accurately adjust for covariates.³⁰ The propensity is of lower complexity than the difficult baseline: $X_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, $e(X_i) = 1/(1 + e^{X_{i2}+X_{i3}})$, $b(X_i) = 2 \log(1 + e^{X_{i1}+X_{i2}+X_{i3}})$.

In these settings I test for dimensions $d \in \{10, 20\}$ and consider relatively small values of $n \in \{500, 1000\}$. The high dimensional case is specified to evaluate how effectively the different methods can learn a smooth heterogeneous treatment effect in the presence of many noise covariates. Because of relatively long runtimes, I restrict analysis to the case $\sigma = 1$. As a performance measure, the average RMSE is computed over 100 repetitions on 2000 randomly drawn test points in the support of the marginal distribution of X .

5.3 Simulation results

The results for Setup 1 in Table 1 verify two observations from earlier simulations: First, the X-learner performs better than the T-learner baseline in an unbalanced setting with both BART and RF as base learners. This is true for both dimensions and sample sizes. Second, BART, which is an estimator that acts globally, has an advantage when the response function is quasi-globally linear or when the data set is small (which is the case in this setup).³¹ Surprisingly, the X-LLF cannot only improve on the X-RF, but also on the X-BART (even under these circumstances), given the presence of many noise covariates, that is $d = 20$. GRF and LLCF are not designed for unbalanced treatment designs and cannot even achieve the performance of the standard X-RF.

Setup 2's results confirm that both LLCF and X-LLF can mitigate the boundary issue discussed in 6.1. However, X-LLF achieves lower RMSE rates among the two in all dimensions and sample sizes, even improving on X-BART, which benefits here again from the small sample sizes.

As expected, the T-learner achieves in most cases the best performance in Setup 3.

³⁰In the literature this is often called "confounding". All of the meta learners discussed here can handle confounding, as long as the ignorability assumption holds.

³¹See KSBYs simulation results.

	d	n	X-BART	T-RF	X-RF	GRF	LLCF	X-LLF
Setup 1	10	500	1.646	4.611	2.211	3.359	3.037	1.785
	10	1000	1.084	4.141	1.417	2.298	2.317	1.298
	20	500	2.391	5.437	3.497	4.086	3.753	1.871
	20	1000	1.447	4.945	2.857	3.52	3.139	1.345
Setup 2	10	500	0.462	0.492	0.517	0.56	0.466	0.266
	10	1000	0.381	0.399	0.402	0.454	0.38	0.189
	20	500	0.528	0.565	0.571	0.619	0.548	0.287
	20	1000	0.435	0.463	0.452	0.509	0.442	0.206
Setup 3	10	500	0.691	0.4	0.42	0.416	0.544	0.509
	10	1000	0.495	0.317	0.305	0.319	0.456	0.359
	20	500	0.766	0.394	0.415	0.416	0.573	0.519
	20	1000	0.552	0.31	0.32	0.329	0.531	0.368
Setup 4	10	500	0.465	0.772	0.27	0.266	0.323	0.218
	10	1000	0.392	0.682	0.209	0.183	0.254	0.164
	20	500	0.498	0.843	0.313	0.32	0.338	0.237
	20	1000	0.423	0.756	0.234	0.209	0.259	0.17

Table 1: Average RMSE of predicting the heterogeneous treatment effect $\tau(x)$ on 100 repetitions of the simulations given above. Sample size $n \in \{500, 1000\}$, covariate vector dimension $d \in \{10, 20\}$, and testing is always on 2000 test points. Errors are reported for the X-learner with BART and random forests as base learners (X-BART, X-RF), the T-learner with random forests as a base learner (T-RF), generalized random forests (GRF), local linear causal forests (LLCF), and the X-learner with local linear forests as base learner (X-LLF). Minimizing errors are reported in bold.

Additionally, X-RF and GRF approach rates similar to the ones of the T-RF.³² Both X-LLF and LLCF perform worse than the standard X-RF and GRF respectively, but X-LLF shows again better behaviour among the two. However, one did not expect these two estimators to perform especially well in this situation, as the CATE is of higher complexity than linear corrections could remove bias. X-BART performs worse than X-RF, as RF capture local complexity better than BART.

Finally, Setup 4 shows that the advantage in boundary correction carries over to situations with confounding, at least for the X-LLF. In all dimensions and sample sizes X-LLF achieves the best results and proves resistance to bias due to an interaction between $e(x)$ and $b(x)$. An interesting insight is that LLCF seems to be inferior to GRF (its own baseline) in this setup. This could possibly be caused by the induced instability of local linear correction under confounding: When estimating the CATE with LLCF, the true covariates to correct on have to be identified. These are usually estimated via a shrinkage estimator (e.g. lasso). Consequently, when the wrong covariates are estimated from the data, the correction is not beneficial anymore and LLCF becomes instable. Even though we have the same correction procedure within

³²This confirms observations for larger sample sizes from KSBYs Simulation 3.

the X-LLF estimator, it seems to yield better estimates due to the structure of its underlying meta-learner.

6 Conclusion

This thesis provided a short overview of common meta-algorithms for CATE estimation, including T-, S-, R- and X-learners, building on the common Neyman-Rubin causal framework. It then reviewed central theoretical findings of the X-learner which was introduced by Künzel et al. (2019). Furthermore, random forests in particular were introduced and discussed as base-learners for the above meta-algorithms with respect to one specific weakness, namely poor performance at the boundaries of the regression surface. Finally, a simulation study was conducted to analyze to which extent a combination of random forests as base learners and local linear regression can enhance the performance of the X-learner. The simulation results suggest that a combination of the local linear random forests (Friedberg et al. (2018)) with the X-learner (KSBY) can effectively counter the bias at boundaries. The X-LLF does not only improve on its own baseline, namely the X-learner equipped with standard random forests, but also beats the similar LLCF suggested by Friedberg et al. (2018) and all other methods in most cases. One exception is the complex treatment function (Setup 3). However, as linear corrections are not optimal in this high complexity scenario, the results underline the necessity of researchers using their subject knowledge when choosing the right base learner. Additionally, due to limitations in computing time, I could only focus on relatively small sample sizes, while simulation 3 in KSBY suggests that the X-learner with random forests can even reach the RMSE-level of the T-learner for large sample sizes in the complex setup. It can therefore be conjectured that the same would also apply here: Both X-RF and X-LLF start off worse compared to the T-RF, but approach its RMSE-level rapidly after increasing n from 500 to 1000. Thus, a general subject for future studies would be the analysis of the X-LLF for larger sample sizes and a larger variety of data-generating processes. Another aim of future research should be the theoretical analysis of the robustness of local linear correction methods with respect to the proposed estimation of treatment effects for various meta-learners. First simulations suggest that there is a high instability paired with worse performance for the LLCF estimator, when a shrinkage estimator of choice is not able to detect the true covariates that contribute to the treatment effect. On the other hand, the X-learner seems to be robuster than LLCF by Friedberg et al. (2018).³³

³³Note that the LLCF achieves a *better* performance than its benchmark, the GRF, in a similar simulation study to our Setup 3 by Friedberg et al. (2018). However, a minor change in their DGP, namely the centering of the baseline effect for our Setup 3, reverses the order of performance and reveals the vulnerability of LLCF. First explorations suggest that the driving factor behind this vulnerability is the said failure to detect the true covariates to correct on.

A Proofs

A.1 Proof of Lemma 1.

This proof is based on the contributions of Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983). Consider observing N independent samples from the distribution \mathcal{P} which is specified by (3): $(Y_i, X_i, W_i)_{i=1}^N \stackrel{iid}{\sim} \mathcal{P}$, with $Y_i = Y_i(W_i)$ under **A4**. Let us follow Künzel et al. (2019) and denote the joint distribution of $(Y_i, X_i, W_i)_{i=1}^N$ by \mathcal{P}^N . Then we will show that under assumption **A1-A4**, $\tau(x)$ can be identified from the joint distribution \mathcal{P}^N . To begin with, let us first state CATEs definition given $X_i = x$:

$$\tau(x) := \mathbb{E}[D_i | X_i = x] = \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0) | X_i = x].$$

Note that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0) | X_i = x] &= \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) | X_i = x] - \mathbb{E}[Y_i(0) | X_i = x] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) | W_i = 1, X_i = x] - \mathbb{E}[Y_i(0) | W_i = 0, X_i = x] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[Y_i | W_i = 1, X_i = x] - \mathbb{E}[Y_i | W_i = 0, X_i = x]. \end{aligned}$$

For the second equality to hold, remember that X_i represents the union of confounding variables and heterogeneity features. Therefore, conditioning on X_i implies conditioning on the confounders and we can use **A1**, that is, the potential outcomes are independent of the treatment indicator. The third equality follows because conditional on the treatment status, the potential outcomes equal the observed outcome (**A4**). Finally, to make estimating the expectations $\mathbb{E}[Y_i | W_i = w, X_i = x]$ for all values of w and x in the support of these variables feasible, we need the overlap assumption (**A2**). If this assumption is violated at some $X_i = x$, it would be impossible to estimate both $\mathbb{E}[Y_i | W_i = 1, X_i = x]$ and $\mathbb{E}[Y_i | W_i = 0, X_i = x]$, because at this point of x there would be either only treated or only control units. However, under these conditions, the CATE is identified from observable data distributed as \mathcal{P}^N .

Note, that an another way to identify $\tau(x)$ is:

$$\tau(x) = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{W_i Y}{e(X_i)} - \frac{(1 - W_i) Y}{1 - e(X_i)} \mid X_i = x\right].^{34}$$

□

A.2 Proof of Lemma 2.

Let $(X, Y), (X_1, Y_1), \dots$ be independent and identically distributed random variables with $\mathbb{E}(Y) < \infty$. Let $O_n = (Y_i, X_i, W_i)_{i=1}^n$ be the set of data according to the distribution of (X, Y) . Let $\hat{\tau}_n : \mathcal{R}^d \mapsto \mathcal{R}$ be a measurable function of x and the data, O_n , that estimates the true treatment effect function $D(x)$. Recall the L_2 risk was

³⁴See chapter 3 in Imbens (2004) for a proof.

specified as

$$\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - D(X))^2 | O_n].$$

Expanding the inner sum yields,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - D(X))^2 | O_n] &= \mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - \tau(X) + \tau(X) - D(X))^2 | O_n] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - \tau(X))^2 | O_n] + \mathbb{E}[(\tau(X) - D(X))^2 | O_n] \\ &\quad + 2 \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - \tau(X))(\tau(X) - D(X)) | O_n]}_A. \end{aligned}$$

Let us examine A :

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \mathbb{E}\left[\mathbb{E}\{(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - \tau(X))(\tau(X) - D(X)) | X\} | O_n\right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - \tau(X))\mathbb{E}\{(\tau(X) - D(X)) | X\} | O_n\right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - \tau(X))(\tau(X) - \tau(X)) | O_n\right] \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\tau}_n(X, O_n) - D(X))^2 | O_n] = \int_{\mathcal{R}^d} (\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n) - \tau(x))^2 \mu(x) + \mathbb{E}[(\tau(X) - D(X))^2]$$

where the integral is called the L_2 error of $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$, μ denotes the distribution of X and the integration is with respect to the Lebesgue measure. When trying to minimize the L_2 risk via $\hat{\tau}^*(\cdot)$, we thus have no influence on the second term on the right side. All we can achieve is to minimize the L_2 error. Thus, the L_2 risk of the estimate $\hat{\tau}_n(x, O_n)$ is close to the optimal value iff the L_2 error is close to zero. \square

A.3 Derivation of the R-learner representation

Recall that the given model can be written according to (4):

$$Y = \mu_0(X) + W \cdot \tau(X) + \gamma(W),$$

where $\gamma(W) = W \cdot \epsilon(1) + (1 - W) \cdot \epsilon(0)$, such that $\mathbb{E}[\gamma(W) | X] = 0$. Furthermore, we can write the conditional mean outcome as:

$$m(X) = \mathbb{E}[Y | X = x] = \mu_0(X) + e(X) \cdot \tau(X) \quad (32)$$

Plugging (32) into (4) and rearranging terms directly yields the decomposition:

$$Y - m(X) = (W - e(X)) \cdot \tau(X) + \gamma(W), \quad (33)$$

This equation can equivalently be expressed as,

$$\tau_{RL}^*(\cdot) = \arg \min_{\tau} \left\{ \mathbb{E} \left[\left((Y - m(X)) - (W - e(X)) \cdot \tau(X) \right)^2 \right] \right\}, \quad (34)$$

which leads immediately to the feasible empirical loss minimization:

$$\hat{\tau}_{RL}(\cdot) = \arg \min_{\tau} \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left((Y_i - \hat{m}(X_i)) - (W_i - \hat{e}(X_i)) \cdot \tau(X_i) \right)^2 + \Lambda_N(\tau(\cdot)) \right\}, \quad (35)$$

using plug-in estimators for $\hat{m}(x)$ and $\hat{e}(x)$. In a last step, expanding the first term and factoring out $W_i - \hat{e}(X_i)$ yields:

$$\hat{\tau}_{RL}(\cdot) = \arg \min_{\tau} \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\underbrace{(W_i - \hat{e}(X_i))^2}_{\hat{w}_i} \left[\underbrace{\frac{Y_i - \hat{m}(X_i)}{W_i - \hat{e}(X_i)}}_{\hat{Y}_i^*} - \tau(X_i) \right]^2 \right) + \Lambda_N(\tau(\cdot)) \right\}. \quad (36)$$

A.4 Derivation of random forests' representation as an adaptive kernel

Recall the random forest estimator at test point x from (28),

$$\hat{f}_{rf}^B(x) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B T(x, \Theta_b),$$

and the response of a single tree at point x (25),

$$T(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{y}_m \mathbb{1}(x \in L_m) = \bar{y}^*.$$

For each single tree of the random forest, the average \bar{y}^* of all training data points assigned to the leaf $L(x)^*$ (the end node which x falls into) can then simply be written as:

$$\bar{y}^* = \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \frac{\mathbb{1}(X_i \in L(x)^*)}{|L(x)^*|} \quad (37)$$

Therefore, it directly follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_{rf}^B(x) &= \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B T(x, \Theta_b) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \bar{y}^* \\ &= \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \frac{\mathbb{1}(X_i \in L(x)^*)}{|L(x)^*|} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \frac{\mathbb{1}(X_i \in L(x)^*)}{|L(x)^*|} = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i(x) Y_i, \end{aligned}$$

where the forest weights $\alpha_i(x)$ is defined as

$$\alpha_i(x) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \frac{\mathbb{1}(X_i \in L(x)^*)}{|L(x)^*|}.$$

A.5 Convergence rate results for the X-learner

The here presented result is based on Künzel et al. (2019)'s Theorem 2. The proof extends the original variant by steps that have been omitted by the authors for convenience. Therefore, as discussed in the main paper above, it covers the case of a linear CATE with $a_\tau = 1$ and no regularity conditions on the response surfaces. Thus, the response surfaces of the first stage can be estimated by any appropriate estimator satisfying the convergence rate a_μ , while the second stage (estimating pseudo-treatment effect functions) estimator is an OLS estimator. From a different perspective, this theorem deals with an example of the case that the underlying distribution \mathcal{P} is assumed to be in some family $F \in S(a_\mu, a_\tau)$ with $a_\tau > a_\mu$. Consequently, one should expect the X-learner to outperform the T-learner in this case.

On the other hand, the case of no conditions on the CATE, but Lipschitz continuous response functions, is as an example of the situation where $a_\mu \approx a_\tau$. KSBY use the X-learner procedure in combination with the KNN estimator to prove it reaching the minimax optimal rate. In this case, both the T-learner and the X-learner achieve the minimax optimal rate; see Theorem 7 in Künzel et al. (2019) for more details and a proof.

A.5.1 Preliminary remark

As in Künzel et al. (2019), results are derived on a superpopulation and conditioned on the number of treated units. This has the advantage to be able to state the performance of estimators in terms of n and m and avoids the possibility to have an empty set of treated units. However, as this leads to nonindependent samples, I follow the authors in specifying three models:

1. Recall the distribution from the main paper \mathcal{P} of (X, W, Y) . I assume to observe N independent samples from \mathcal{P} and denote the joint distribution as,

$$(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N \sim \mathcal{P}^N. \quad (38)$$

2. For the technical results, it is helpful to consider the conditional distribution of the sample given a fixed number n of treated units:

$$\left[(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N \mid \sum_{i=1}^N W_i = n \right] \sim \mathcal{P}^{nm}. \quad (39)$$

Here, due to conditioning on the number of treated units, the (X_i, W_i, Y_i) lose their independency, but are still identical in distribution.

3. The third distribution that is needed is:

$$\left[(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N \mid W = w \right] \sim \mathcal{P}^w \quad (40)$$

Under this distribution (X_i, Y_i) are not identical in distribution (as W determines the group), but the authors show that within each treatment group (X_i, Y_i) tuples are still iid (see Theorem 3 in KSBY for a proof of this claim).

Let me first state a Lemma needed for the main proof:

Lemma 3. *Let \mathcal{P} be defined as in (3) with $0 < e_{\min} < e(x) < e_{\max} < 1$. Let X, W be distributed according to \mathcal{P} , and let g be a positive function such that the expectations below exist; then*

$$\frac{e_{\min}}{e_{\max}} \mathbb{E}[g(X)] \leq \mathbb{E}[g(X) \mid W = 1] \leq \frac{e_{\max}}{e_{\min}} \mathbb{E}[g(X)], \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{1 - e_{\max}}{1 - e_{\min}} \mathbb{E}[g(X)] \leq \mathbb{E}[g(X) \mid W = 0] \leq \frac{1 - e_{\min}}{1 - e_{\max}} \mathbb{E}[g(X)]. \quad (42)$$

Proof. Let us start with (41). The lower bound follows from

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[g(X) \mid W = 1] &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(x) f_{X|W}(x \mid W = 1) dx = \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(x) \frac{f_{X,W}(x, W = 1)}{P(W = 1)} dx \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(x) \frac{f_X(x) P(W = 1 \mid X = x)}{\mathbb{E}[W]} dx = \frac{1}{\mathbb{E}[W]} \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(x) f_X(x) e(x) dx \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\mathbb{E}[W]} \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(x) f_X(x) \inf_x e(x) dx = \frac{\inf_x e(x)}{\mathbb{E}[W]} \mathbb{E}[g(X)] \\ &\geq \frac{e_{\min}}{\mathbb{E}[W]} \mathbb{E}[g(X)] \geq \frac{e_{\min}}{e_{\max}} \mathbb{E}[g(X)], \end{aligned}$$

where the last weak inequality follows from:

$$\mathbb{E}[W] = P(W = 1) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} P(W = 1 \mid X = x) f_X(x) dx \leq \int_{\mathcal{X}} e_{\max} f_X(x) dx = e_{\max}.$$

The upper bound follows analogously by replacing the infimum with the supremum of the propensity function $e(x)$, such that the inequality goes to the other direction. Finally, (42) follows from a symmetrical argument.

Theorem 2. *Assume we observe m control units and n treated units from some super population of independent and identically distributed observations $(Y(0), Y(1), X, W)$ coming from a distribution \mathcal{P} given in (3) that satisfies the following assumptions:*

C1 *The error terms ϵ_i are independent given X , with $\mathbb{E}[\epsilon_i \mid X = x] = 0$ and $\text{Var}[\epsilon_i \mid X = x] \leq \sigma^2$.*

C2 X has finite second moments,

$$\mathbb{E}[\|X\|_2^2] \leq C_X.$$

C3 Assumptions **A1** - **A4** hold.

C4 There exists an estimator $\hat{\mu}_0^m$ and $a > 0$ with

$$EMSE(\mathcal{P}, \hat{\mu}_0^m) = \mathbb{E}[(\mu_0(X) - \hat{\mu}_0^m(X))^2] \leq C_0 m^{-a}.$$

C5 The treatment effect is parametrically linear, $\tau(x) = x^T \beta$, with $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

C6 The eigenvalues of the sample covariance matrix of X^1 , $\hat{\Sigma}_n = \frac{1}{n}(X^1)'X^1$, where X^1 is the matrix consisting of the features of treated units, are well conditioned, in the sense that there exists an n_0 , such that

$$\sup_{n > n_0} \gamma_{\min}^{-1}(\hat{\Sigma}_n) \leq C_\Sigma.$$

Then the X -learner with $\hat{\mu}_0^m$ in the first stage, OLS in the second stage and weight function $g \equiv 0$ has the following upper bound on its EMSE: for all $n > n_0$,

$$EMSE(\mathcal{P}, \hat{\tau}^{mn}) = \mathbb{E}[\|(\tau(X) - \hat{\tau}^{mn}(X))\|^2] \leq C(m^{-a} + n^{-1}) \quad (43)$$

with $C = \max(c_2 C_0, \sigma^2 d) C_X C_\Sigma$. In particular, if there are a lot of control units, such that $m \geq c_3 n^{1/a}$, then the X -learner achieves the parametric rate in n ,

$$EMSE(\mathcal{P}, \hat{\tau}^{mn}) \leq (1 + c_3) C n^{-1}. \quad (44)$$

As symmetric argument for the last part holds, if n is much larger than m . Before beginning the proof, note that for this theorem to hold, the EMSE of $\hat{\mu}_0$ must converge at a rate of a , but not necessarily the MSE at every x . Let $(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N$ be iid from \mathcal{P} as in (38) and \mathcal{P}^{nm} the conditional distribution of $(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N$ given that we observe n treated units as in (39). We are interested in the performance of the X -learner, $\hat{\tau}_{XL}^{mn}$ under \mathcal{P}^{nm} as measured by the EMSE (this is equivalent to the conditional expected L_2 error (see (16)):

$$EMSE(\mathcal{P}^{nm}, \hat{\tau}_{XL}^{mn}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{E}\left[(\hat{\tau}_{XL}^{mn}(\mathcal{X}) - \tau(\mathcal{X}))^2 \mid \sum_{i=1}^N W_i = n\right]. \quad (45)$$

Again, the expectation is taken over the training data set $(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N \sim \mathcal{P}^{nm}$, and \mathcal{X} , which is distributed according to the marginal distribution of X in \mathcal{P} . Note that in this setup, \mathcal{X} is independent of $(X_i, W_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^N$.³⁵ Note also, that $g \equiv 0$ in

³⁵The distribution \mathcal{P}^{nm} never relies on \mathcal{X} , see also ‘‘Framework and Definitions’’ in KSBY.

the theorem implies that the X-learner here is equal to $\hat{\tau}_1$, which means that we can restrict the theoretical analysis *w.l.o.g.* to the performance of $\hat{\tau}_1$. Therefore, to simplify notation, I write X instead of X^1 for the observed covariates of the treated units.

Proof. First of all, let me write the imputed treatment effects of the second stage for the treatment group as

$$\begin{aligned} D_i^1 &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} Y_i - \hat{\mu}_0(X_i) = \mu_1(X_i) + \epsilon_i - \hat{\mu}_0(X_i) \\ &= X_i^T \beta + \mu_0(X_i) - \hat{\mu}_0(X_i) + \epsilon_i = X_i^T \beta + \delta_i + \epsilon_i, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where for the third equality we used assumption **C5**, i.e.,

$$\tau(X_i) = \mu_1(X_i) - \mu_0(X_i) = X_i^T \beta,$$

and $\delta_i = \mu_0(X_i) - \hat{\mu}_0(X_i)$. Recall further that β is estimated by an OLS estimator, such that,

$$\hat{\beta} = (X'X)^{-1}X'D^1, \quad (47)$$

and simplify the notation by defining the event of observing n treated units as $E_n = \{\sum_{i=1}^N W_i = n\}$. Start now by decomposing the EMSE in two orthogonal error terms:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[(\tau(\mathcal{X}) - \hat{\tau}_{XL}(\mathcal{X}))^2 \mid E_n\right] &= \mathbb{E}\left[(\mathcal{X}(\beta - \hat{\beta}))^2 \mid E_n\right] \stackrel{\text{Cauchy-Schwarz}}{\leq} \mathbb{E}\left[\|\mathcal{X}\|^2 \|\beta - \hat{\beta}\|^2 \mid E_n\right] \\ &\stackrel{\perp}{=} \mathbb{E}\left[\|\mathcal{X}\|^2\right] \mathbb{E}\left[\|\beta - \hat{\beta}\|^2 \mid E_n\right] \\ &\stackrel{(46,47)}{=} \mathbb{E}\left[\|\mathcal{X}\|^2\right] \mathbb{E}\left[\|(X'X)^{-1}X'\delta + (X'X)^{-1}X'\epsilon\|^2 \mid E_n\right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}\left[\|\mathcal{X}\|^2\right] \mathbb{E}\left[\underbrace{\|(X'X)^{-1}X'\delta\|^2}_{:= A} + \underbrace{\|(X'X)^{-1}X'\epsilon\|^2}_{:= B} \mid E_n\right], \end{aligned}$$

where I used the subadditivity of the norm in the last inequality. Assuming through the proof that $n > n_0$ enables us to use assumption **C6**. Let us use the additivity of the expectation and start analysing the second term B :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[\|(X'X)^{-1}X'\epsilon\|^2 \mid E_n\right] &= \mathbb{E}\left[\epsilon'X(X'X)^{-1}(X'X)^{-1}X'\epsilon \mid E_n\right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\text{tr}(X(X'X)^{-1}(X'X)^{-1}X'\epsilon\epsilon') \mid E_n\right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\text{tr}((X'X)^{-1}(X'X)^{-1}X'X \mathbb{E}[\epsilon\epsilon' \mid X, E_n]) \mid E_n\right] \\ &\leq \sigma^2 \mathbb{E}\left[\text{tr}((X'X)^{-1}) \mid E_n\right]. \end{aligned}$$

For the next step, note that since $\hat{\Sigma}_n = \frac{1}{n}(X^1)'X^1$ is normal, the spectral theorem applies and there exist matrices Γ and Λ , such that:

$$\hat{\Sigma}_n = \Gamma\Lambda\Gamma', \quad (48)$$

where the entries of the diagonal matrix Λ are the eigenvalues of $\hat{\Sigma}_n$ and the column vectors of Γ are the orthogonal eigenvectors of $\hat{\Sigma}_n$. Also note that this implies:

$$(X'X)^{-1} = \frac{1}{n} \Gamma \Lambda^{-1} \Gamma'. \quad (49)$$

As the sum of the d eigenvalues of $\hat{\Sigma}_n$ is the same as its trace, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^2 \mathbb{E}[\text{tr}((X'X)^{-1}) \mid E_n] &= \sigma^2 \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^d \gamma_i^{-1}(\hat{\Sigma}_n) \mid E_n\right] \\ &\leq \frac{\sigma^2}{n} \mathbb{E}\left[d \gamma_{\min}^{-1}(\hat{\Sigma}_n) \mid E_n\right] \leq \sigma^2 d C_\Sigma n^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where we used assumption **C6** for the last inequality. Next, I want to bound the error in A , coming from not perfectly predicting μ_0 :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|(X'X)^{-1} X' \delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n] &= \mathbb{E}[\|X^{-1} X (X'X)^{-1} X' \delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}[\|X^{-1}\|_2^2 \|X (X'X)^{-1} X'\|_2^2 \|\delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[\gamma_{\min}^{-1}(X'X) \|X (X'X)^{-1} X'\|_2^2 \|\delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n], \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

where, for the inequality, I used the sub-multiplicativity of the spectral norm and its compatibility with the euclidean vector norm (the spectral norm is induced by the euclidean vector norm and thus compatible by definition). The equality follows from the fact that, if X is invertible, then

$$\|X^{-1}\|_2^2 = \gamma_{\min}^{-1}(X'X).$$

Now, since $M := X(X'X)^{-1} X'$ is an idempotent matrix it has only eigenvalues of zero and one. Also, as the matrix is normal, its norm is equal to one:

$$\|M\|_2^2 = \gamma_{\max}(M'M) = 1.$$

Thus (51) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} (52) &= \mathbb{E}[\gamma_{\min}^{-1}(X'X) \|\delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n] = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{n} \gamma_{\min}^{-1}(\hat{\Sigma}_n) \|\delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n\right] \leq \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}[C_\Sigma \|\delta\|_2^2 \mid E_n] \\ &= \frac{1}{n} C_\Sigma \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i^2(X_i) \mid E_n\right] = \frac{1}{n} C_\Sigma n \mathbb{E}[\|\delta_1\|_2^2 \mid E_n] = C_\Sigma \mathbb{E}[\|\delta_1\|_2^2 \mid E_n]. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

Here the second equality follows from an argument similar to (49), while the inequality comes from assumption **C6**. Note that,

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\delta_1\|_2^2 \mid E_n] = \mathbb{E}[\|\mu_0(X_1) - \hat{\mu}_0(X_1)\|_2^2 \mid E_n, W_1 = 1] = \mathbb{E}[g(X_1) \mid E_n, W_1 = 1]. \quad (53)$$

Applying (41) and (42), and assumption **C4** directly yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[g(X_1) \mid E_n, W_1 = 1\right] &\leq \frac{e_{max}}{e_{min}} \frac{1 - e_{min}}{1 - e_{max}} \mathbb{E}\left[\|\mu_0(X_1) - \hat{\mu}_0(X_1)\|_2^2 \mid E_n, W_1 = 0\right] \\ &\leq \frac{e_{max} - e_{max}e_{min}}{e_{min} - e_{max}e_{min}} C_0 m^{-a_\mu} = c_2 C_0 m^{-a_\mu}, \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

with $c_2 := (e_{max} - e_{max}e_{min}) / (e_{min} - e_{max}e_{min})$. Finally, one can use assumption **C2** that $\mathbb{E}\left[\|\mathcal{X}\|^2 \mid E_n\right] \leq C_{\mathcal{X}}$ to conclude:

$$\mathbb{E}\left[(\tau(\mathcal{X}) - \hat{\tau}_{XL}(\mathcal{X}))^2 \mid E_n\right] \leq C_{\mathcal{X}} \left(c_2 C_\Sigma C_0 m^{-a_\mu} + \sigma^2 d C_\Sigma n^{-1} \right).$$

□

B Tuning details

General random forests (GRF) as implemented by the “grf” package are tuned via the automatic self-tuning feature and local linear causal forests (LLCF) are tuned via cross-validation. The identification of relevant covariates to correct on (for LLCF and X-LLF) is done via 10-fold cross-validation and the “glmnet” R package, which fits a generalized linear model via penalized maximum likelihood. X-BART is not cross-validated, because the authors recommend X-BART specifically for when a user does not want to carefully tune. Due to the amount of hyperparameters, X-RF is not cross-validated. However, I follow KSBY in parts of their simulation study in choosing preset hyperparameters that they used in the 2016 Atlantic Causal Inference Conference competition and that performed considerably well in most scenarios. I acknowledge that this may hinder X-BART’s and X-RF’s performance. While for X-RF and X-BART methods from “causalToolbox” are used, the various steps in X-LLF were manually implemented holding the base-learner constant (local linear forests). These local linear forests in each step of X-LLF are tuned via the automatic self-tuning feature.

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„Ich versichere hiermit, dass ich die vorstehende Bachelorarbeit selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe, dass die vorgelegte Arbeit noch an keiner anderen Hochschule zur Prüfung vorgelegt wurde und dass sie weder ganz noch in Teilen bereits veröffentlicht wurde. Wörtliche Zitate und Stellen, die anderen Werken dem Sinn nach entnommen sind, habe ich in jedem einzelnen Fall kenntlich gemacht.“

Bonn, 07.07.2019

